

(Re)imagining the future of faculty PD

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How can we (re)imagine the future of faculty professional development where meaningful work takes place across functional boundaries? How can we intentionally build the common ground necessary for effective and comprehensive faculty development?

Alexandra's research into Centres for Teaching and Learning in the US and Europe has revealed a variety of patterns for the relation between CTLs and educational technology teams (with their various names and identities). This workshop drew on this research and kicked off with a short presentation outlining the most relevant models encountered. Participants then worked in small groups on exploring various scenarios aimed at developing strategies for enhancing internal coherence as well as the impact on the teaching quality and student experience at the respective institution.

The subsequent plenary discussion aimed to bring together the strategies linked to the different models and enable participants to better understand what is necessary to make the work of these teams – merged, separate or collaborating – effective given the specific institutional context.

This workshop was targeted towards professionals working in staff development, both on the technology and pedagogy side (in or outside CTLs), as well as representatives of university management in charge of faculty professional development and/ or educational technology implementation.

(We conducted this workshop in one synchronous session (90 minutes), but an alternative could be a blended session, starting with asynchronous work and discussions and culminating with the synchronous part.)

Suggested reading

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